

COMBINED FINITE ELEMENT METHOD AND MACHINE LEARNING TOWARD ANALYSIS OF MYOCARDIAL ISCHEMIA

Smiljana Tomašević^{1,2}, Marko Robnik-Šikonja³, Nenad Filipović^{1,2}

¹ Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac, Sestre Janjić 6, 34000 Kragujevac

² Bioengineering Research and Development Center, Prvoslava Stojanovića 6, 34000 Kragujevac
e-mail: smiljana@kg.ac.rs, fica@kg.ac.rs

³ Faculty of Computer and Information Science, University of Ljubljana, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia
e-mail: marko.robnik@fri.uni-lj.si

Abstract

This study combines Finite Element Method (FEM) and machine learning (ML) with aim to i) computationally simulate myocardial ischemia and, afterwards, ii) automatically detect and localize its presence. The computed tomography (CT) images are used to create a simplified 3D FE heart-torso model. A 3D FE model of the heart is segmented on 17 zones, enabling simulation of normal and ischemic cardiac beats in different zones and creation of a virtual database which is furtherly used for ML approach. Several classifiers are trained and tested using the virtual database to detect and localize ischemic beats based on the body surface potentials map (BSPM). If the ECG signal is classified as ischemic at the first stage ML model, potentials are processed by the second stage, which predicts the location of the ischemic area in one of the heart's segments. The proposed approach presents an improved solution which can facilitate daily clinical practice and enable timely treatment planning in future.

Key words: myocardial ischemia, finite element method, machine learning

1. Introduction

Myocardial ischemia is most common cause of death, presenting a restriction in blood supply to heart tissue due to a partial or complete blockage of a coronary artery under atherosclerosis [1]. It is usually diagnosed by analysing ST deviations in patient's ECGs, but there is strong evidence in clinical practice that ischemic regions cannot be localized using 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG). Last years, different computational methods have been developed to simulate heart's function and generation of body surface potential maps (BSPMs), as well as inversely model the cardiac activities (i.e., ECGs). With aim to facilitate clinical application of computational solutions, the presented study combines two approaches - Finite Element Method (FEM) and Machine Learning (ML) alleviating limitations of their separate usage. The first step includes creation of virtual database of normal and ischemic cardiac beats employing FEM, while the second step covers the localisation of detected ischemic cardiac beats using ML.

2. Materials and method

In order to perform FE simulations of normal and ischemic cardiac beats, a simplified 3D FE heart-torso model is created using Computed Tomography (CT) images. Torso is assumed to be completely homogeneous, while 3D FE model of the heart is segmented on 17 zones [2], enabling simulation of ischemic and non-ischemic cardiac beats in different zones. Normal and ischemic beats are simulated by applying adequate values of electrical potentials within the heart, which propagates to the body surface. In this way, the virtual measurements are stored into the database which consists of 1700 instances (850 ischemic patients and 850 non-ischemic patients). Several classifiers are trained and tested using the virtual database to detect and localize ischemic cardiac beats based on the BSPM. If the ECG signal is classified as ischemic at the first stage ML model, potentials are processed by the second stage, which predicts the location of the ischemic area in one of the heart's segments. We analysed our dataset with two approaches for model automation: Bayesian model selection with Auto-WEKA tool [3] and caret package in R [4].

3. Results and Conclusions

In the detection of cardiac ischemia (the first phase model), Random forest model applied on the test set returned the best classification accuracy (94.7%), while the other methods achieved somewhat lower accuracy (from 93.2% to 93.8%). The second phase model determined the correct location of cardiac ischemia with 89% accuracy and it was, surprisingly, the linear discriminant analysis (LDA) which turned out to be the best classifier, taking into account that almost 10% of the testing set are misclassified with the first stage classifier. Other ensemble-based classifiers (mars, xgbT, xgbL, gbm, and rf) achieved somewhat lower classification accuracy. It can be said that the results of the second phase modelling are good and allow successful practical application of the proposed system.

In summary, this study reported the investigation of myocardial ischemic detection and localisation employing FEM and ML approach, integrating the bidomain heart model with the monodomain torso model. It presents an improved solution which can facilitate daily clinical practice and enable timely treatment planning in future. More complex models and simulations, as well as finer calculations of electrical potentials will be in focus of our further studies.

Acknowledgement: This work is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 952603 (SGABU). This article reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The work is also funded by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, contract number [451-03-68/2022-14/200107 (Faculty of Engineering, University of Kragujevac)].

References

- [1] Benjamin EJ, Muntner P, Alonso A, Bittencourt MS, Callaway CW, Carson AP, Chamberlain AM, Chang AR, Cheng S, Das SR, Delling FN, Heart disease and stroke statistics-2019 update: a report from the American Heart Association. *Circulation* 5;139(10):e56-28, 2019.
- [2] Cerqueira MD, Weissman NJ, Dilsizian V, Jacobs AK, Kaul S, Laskey WK, Pennell DJ, Ryan T, Verani MS, Standardized myocardial segmentation and nomenclature for tomographic imaging of the heart. *Circulation* 105, 539–542, 2002.
- [3] Kotthoff L, Thornton C, Hoos HH, Hutter F, Leyton-Brown K, Auto-WEKA 2.0: Automatic model selection and hyperparameter optimization in WEKA. *The Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 18(25):1-5, 2017.
- [4] Kuhn, M. Building predictive models in R using the caret package. *Journal of statistical software* 28:1-26, 2008.